

Consequences of a Particle at X and a Force Acting Over dx and Quantum Mechanics

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Classical Newtonian mechanics separates a particle (effect) from a force (cause). A particle has properties at a given x (and time t), but if it interacts with a force, this interaction occurs over dt and dx . Given that many forces do not change in time, we argue that a notion of a force is inseparable from the idea of dx . If one gives the value of a force at x , this value acts within a dx , which in Newtonian mechanics tends to 0.

We have argued before that a particle with momentum represents a force or impulse itself, but at the same time may receive impulse hits from other sources (e.g. a Newtonian force $-dV/dx$). If a particle represents a force(impulse) it should be inseparable from the notion of dx , even if it has a constant p (momentum) and is traveling through space. Thus the idea of a momentum defining an internal ruler gradation through a probability distribution in x which we have presented in previous notes is compatible with the idea of describing a particle as a force. If one only considers a particle as an effect, there would be no need to worry about dx until a force(x) appears.

An internal dx is not defined by an external ruler and does not need to tend to 0 as in Newtonian mechanics. Rather it is statistical in nature as p is a fixed impulse, but the probability to be at different x points within dx (called a wavelength) differ. In (1) we compared a classical Maxwell-Boltzmann gas to a quantum free particle. We argued that d/d density Pressure = RT = average pressure of a particle. We suggested this is analogous to the quantum free particle situation: $(-i\hbar/dx \text{ probability}(p,x)) / \text{probability}(p,x) = p$ where $\text{probability}(p,x)$ is unnormalized. In other words a change in a probability yields a deterministic value p .

The notion of a deterministic value p associated with a probability distribution in what would be another deterministic variable x in Newtonian mechanics (except now one has a dx distribution because the particle is a force/impulse) has consequences. If one wishes to have a particle sit at $x=0$, say in an oscillator system, one needs to use a wavelength which is fairly small and centered at $x=0$. The wavelength, however, is associated with momentum and even being small spreads out from $x=0$ meaning there is potential energy $.5kx^2$ as well. Thus one may use an ensemble of forces/impulses $\sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ to create a “ dx ” about $x=0$, but at the same time this ensemble represents an average particle (defined at x with $\text{prms}(x)$) which must satisfy $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$ i.e. the classical conservation expression. In other words, one sees again that average statistical quantities may behave as deterministic ones.

Classical Newtonian Mechanics and “dx”

Classical mechanics treats a particle as an effect and gives its properties at x and t . One also has $x(t)$. The particle is acted on by a force which interacts over dx and dt , but these are assumed to tend to 0. Thus even in Newtonian mechanics, a force is associated with dx and not just a point x , even though one writes force(x). Furthermore, action-reaction in Newtonian mechanics suggests the particle is also like a force. If it has momentum, it represents an impulse and so should be associated with a dx . What dx , however, exists for a particle with

constant momentum? It seems the particle needs to “create” its own dx and this requires a probability distribution with zero values at the endpoints of dx . It further means one does not have deterministic behaviour, but rather probabilistic within dx , although on average motion over the various adjacent dx 's has the appearance of deterministic behaviour i.e. $dx = v dt$. Dx is called a wavelength for a particle with constant p and given by \hbar/p as will be seen in a later section.

Notion of an Extremization Problem

Above we argued that a particle represents a force/impulse and so must create its own associated dx which may only be done through a probability distribution in x within $dx = \hbar/p$. We argued that this probabilistic picture is similar to that of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with Pressure = density(x) RT where density(x) = N densityOneParticle(x) and N = the number of particles. Pressure is linked to RT, a single particle pressure and its spatial density (probability). Changing the spatial density of a single particle (i.e. its x probability) changes the pressure. Pressure itself, however, is an average quantity i.e. the average of $p v$ where v = velocity. For a single particle with “ dx ” this seems to be equivalent to:

$$\text{Single particle impulse} = p = \text{change } x\text{-probability} \{ \text{probability}(x) * p \} \quad ((1))$$

One, however, cannot change the “number” of particles for a single particle, so the change x -probability should be linked with d/dx . In such a case, ((1)) becomes:

$$p = d/dx \text{ Probability} / \text{Probability} \quad \text{because probability is unnormalized.} \quad ((2))$$

((2)) leads to $\exp(ipx) = \text{unnormalized probability}$, hence the wavelength = \hbar/p used above.

Like $\text{singleparticle density}(x) RT$ representing average single particle pressure, $p \exp(ipx)$ represents average single particle impulse when divided by the normalization factor. $p \exp(ipx)$, however, is an unnormalized average impulse in space.

The d/dx procedure described above is identical to an extremization problem such as Fermat's least time principle where x becomes a changeable value associated with a constant $p(x)$ component). Extremization of a variable quantity (probabilistic) yields a deterministic one in the quantum case. In the classical case, it yields RT, the average pressure of a single particle, but E_{ave} is taken to be very close to E_{total} (i.e. the variance is very small) so RT is really treated as a deterministic quantity.

The idea of x and p as unrelated precisely known values in classical mechanics disappears within a dx i.e. wavelength. “ X ” becomes a stochastic quantity. This leads to a reevaluation of classical notions such as a particle on a spring at $x=0$.

The Notion of Ground State Energy

A classical particle may exist at a point x . We have argued that a particle, however, represents a force/impulse and must be linked with a dx . We call this dx wavelength and define it as \hbar/p . Thus there is a specific x -spread associated with each p . As p becomes smaller, the spread is larger. For a particle on a spring at $x=0$, however, one requires the x spread to be as small as possible. This means it must be associated with a momentum or average momentum i.e. $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Given an x -spread, there will be potential energy values $.5kxx$ as well as the average kinetic energy represented by the p 's. The spring is linked with the classical energy conservation equation :

$$KE(x) + .5kxx = \text{Energy } ((3)).$$

Thus the statistical x -spread associated with the particle which acts as a force-impulse, must now be linked with a point type particle which satisfies ((3)) i.e. no longer has a spread. Thus the same particle is represented in two different ways;

((A)) The particle has an x -spread given by the average $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ i.e. $W^*(x)W(x)xx - 0 = \text{variance}$

((B)) At the same time, one may use $W(x)$ to define classical averages which exist at the point x i.e. $KE = \{-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W\}$.

Solving ((3)) for the lowest energy yields a spread about 0 which at the same time satisfies the classical conservation of energy equation albeit with the particle being represented by $\text{prms}(x)$ and x . As a result, the lowest energy is not 0 as in the classical case, but there is a minimum ground state energy.

One sees again, how statistical quantities such as $\text{prms}(x)$ may play the role of a kind of deterministic quantity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a classical particle with momentum p should also represent a force/impulse and be associated with a dx as force(x) is. How does this "dx" emerge? We argue it is linked with a probability distribution in x i.e. a given p (momentum) is associated with a physical dx created through a probability. This seems to be similar to a notion found in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas: Pressure = $N \text{ singleparticledensity}(x) RT$. Varying $\text{singleparticledensity}(x)$ yields RT , the average pressure of a single particle. We suggest that for a single particle one may only vary $\text{singleparticledensity}$ by using d/dx . Calling $\text{singleparticledensity}$, $P(p,x)$ and treating it as unnormalized yields $d/dx P / P = p$ or $P = \exp(ipx)$. Thus dx is \hbar/p . (actually constant/ p). As a result, a deterministic quantity p is associated with changes in a probabilistic one. As a result, a constant p creates a spatial resolution.

We next consider a particle on a spring at $x=0$. If \hbar/p is the wavelength or x -spread, and one wants this to be small, one requires a certain p , i.e. some kinetic energy even at $x=0$. One may create the average $W(x) = \text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(kpx)$ as representing a spread about $x=0$, but this contains average kinetic energy and also potential energy $.5kxx$. An average particle (with averaged spreads) creates averages at an x point which satisfy Newtonian conservation of energy. Thus there is a probabilistic x -spread associated with each p , but p and x , i.e. averages become “deterministic” quantities in the classical conservation of energy equation.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas Pressure Ideas Applied to a Single Particle Yields $\exp(ipx)$? (preprint, zenodo, 2023)